

EBFMC25-OP-72 · BRCA1 Mutation and Advanced Stage Ovarian Cancer Due to Prophylactic Surgery Refusal

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Epithelial ovarian cancer is typically diagnosed at an advanced stage and has the highest mortality rate among gynecological cancers. Although population-based screening methods have proven ineffective, molecular genetic approaches offer promising strategies for early diagnosis and prevention (Lheureux, Gourley et al. 2019). BRCA mutations play a critical role in ovarian cancer.

Case Presentation: In our case, a 51-year-old female patient underwent genetic testing due to a family history of cancer, revealing a BRCA1 exon 18-19 heterozygous deletion. Prophylactic surgery was recommended but refused by the patient, who also did not continue follow-up.

Discussion: Later, the patient developed peritonitis carcinomatosa. Following surgery and adjuvant chemotherapy, olaparib treatment was initiated, achieving a complete response.

Conclusion: This case highlights the crucial role of genetic risk factors such as BRCA mutation positivity in cancer prophylaxis and treatment strategies.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Ovarian cancer, BRCA Mutations, PARP Inhibitors

INTRODUCTION

Ovarian cancer is the fifth most common cancer and the fourth leading cause of cancer-related death in women. Due to the lack of specific symptoms, 75% of cases are diagnosed at an advanced stage. Most of these cases involve aggressive tumors of serous histology, originating from the fimbrial end of the fallopian tubes (Obstetricians and Gynecologists 2017). The lifetime risk of developing ovarian cancer in the general population is approximately 1 in 54, but it is significantly higher in individuals carrying BRCA mutations (Ledermann, Raja et al. 2013). However, 44% of patients with BRCA mutations report no family history of cancer (Alsop, Fereday et al. 2012). The prevalence of BRCA1 mutations is approximately 1 in 300, while BRCA2 mutations occur in about 1 in 800 individuals, though these rates are higher in certain ethnic groups (Goetsch, Wicklund et al. 2016). In populations with increased genetic predisposition, particularly in regions with higher rates of consanguineous marriages, the frequency of these mutations may be elevated.

Although ovarian cancer is typically diagnosed after the age of 50, patients with BRCA mutations tend to develop the disease at an earlier age and have a higher estimated lifetime risk (Bolton, Chenevix-Trench et al. 2012). While BRCA1-associated ovarian cancers tend to be more aggressive, some studies suggest that they respond better to first-line taxol-carboplatin chemotherapy compared to sporadic cases (Vencken, Kriege et al. 2011).

BRCA1 mutations impair homologous recombination, a key DNA repair mechanism, leading to genomic instability and malignant transformation. BRCA1 and BRCA2 mutations are inherited in an autosomal dominant pattern, with a 50% chance of being passed on to offspring. These mutations increase the risk of breast and ovarian cancers, as well as pancreatic, prostate, and melanoma cancers (Mutch and DiSaia 2007). In ovarian cancer patients, approximately 15-20% of pathogenic BRCA mutations are somatic, while 80-85%

are germline (Ledermann, Harter et al. 2014). BRCA mutation testing can be performed on blood and saliva samples (germline) or on tumor tissue (somatic) (Vergote, Banerjee et al. 2016).

Prophylactic mastectomy and oophorectomy significantly reduce cancer risk in BRCA mutation carriers. These preventive strategies are crucial for reducing cancer incidence before it develops. In BRCA-mutated ovarian cancer patients, standard surgical and chemotherapy protocols are complemented by the use of PARP inhibitors, such as olaparib, which target DNA repair deficiencies in cancer cells, thereby exploiting their vulnerability (Vergote, Banerjee et al. 2016). Although prophylactic surgery refusal does not necessarily reduce mortality risk, early detection and monitoring strategies are essential.

Thus, identifying BRCA mutations is a key step in risk assessment and treatment planning, making genetic screening recommended for all epithelial ovarian cancer patients.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 51-year-old unmarried female patient, a university graduate, was diagnosed with ovarian cancer at an external center and was referred to our clinic after surgery. Her medical history revealed that in 2019, her sister was diagnosed with ovarian cancer, leading to BRCA testing for both siblings. The patient was found to have a heterozygous deletion in BRCA1 exon 18-19, while BRCA2 was normal. At that time, prophylactic mastectomy and total abdominal hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy (TAH-BSO) were recommended, but the patient declined due to concerns about psychological distress. She also did not undergo regular follow-up.

In May 2023, she presented with abdominal pain and bloating. Imaging studies revealed peritonitis carcinomatosa, leading to her referral to Ondokuz Mayıs University Hospital. Abdominal MRI confirmed peritoneal carcinomatosis with ascites but no ovarian mass. The tumor was suspected to be of tubal origin. Cytological analysis of ascitic fluid (OMÜ-3290/23) confirmed high-grade serous carcinoma, with 60% ER positivity and diffuse p53 positivity. The patient underwent TAH-BSO, splenectomy, total omentectomy, low anterior resection (LAR), diaphragmatic excision, total peritonectomy, and tumor excision from the bowel serosa and mesentery. Pathology confirmed serous carcinoma, FIGO stage IIIC, with malignant peritoneal washings. Postoperatively, she received six cycles of carboplatin-paclitaxel chemotherapy, followed by maintenance therapy with olaparib due to her BRCA mutation status. The patient remains under follow-up with no evidence of recurrence.

DISCUSSION

Ovarian cancer lacks specific symptoms or physical examination findings and is often diagnosed at an advanced stage. Routine screening methods have not been effective in reducing ovarian cancer mortality (Jacobs, Menon et al. 2016). Identifying at-risk individuals and implementing preventive interventions remain the most effective strategies. Therefore, genetic testing for BRCA mutations is recommended for newly diagnosed epithelial ovarian cancer patients.

BRCA mutations compromise DNA repair, increasing the risk of malignancy. The cumulative lifetime risk for ovarian cancer is 35-46% for BRCA1 mutation carriers and 11% for BRCA2 carriers (Selçuk, Özel et al. 2018). A large study analyzing 8,139 ovarian cancer cases identified BRCA mutations in 500 patients, revealing that while BRCA1 carriers had a decreasing risk of breast cancer with age, BRCA2 carriers did not exhibit the same trend (Antoniou, Pharoah et al. 2003).

For BRCA1 carriers, risk-reducing surgery is recommended between ages 35-40 or after childbearing is complete, whereas BRCA2 carriers may delay surgery until ages 40-45. In patients refusing prophylactic surgery, transvaginal ultrasonography and CA-125 monitoring may be performed, though these measures have not been proven to reduce mortality (Hermsen, Olivier et al. 2007). In advanced ovarian cancer, standard treatment includes cytoreductive surgery and platinum-based chemotherapy. Unfortunately, disease recurrence occurs in 70% of cases within three years. PARP inhibitors have emerged as a significant therapeutic option, particularly in BRCA-mutated cases, by inducing DNA damage accumulation and promoting cancer cell death (O'Connor 2015). Olaparib is FDA and EMA-approved for maintenance therapy in platinum-sensitive relapsed ovarian cancer and is also indicated for advanced-stage cases after multiple chemotherapy regimens (Stewart, George et al. 2018).

Ovarian cancer remains the most lethal gynecological malignancy. Screening programs, genetic analyses, and preventive interventions are essential for reducing mortality rates. Genetic counseling and testing should be

provided to all high-risk individuals. Moreover, targeted therapies such as PARP inhibitors improve treatment outcomes in BRCA-mutated patients.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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